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The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob

Nirupama Suneetha¹

Abstract

It is indeed paradoxical that Kerala, with its long history of immigration, has very little to show as immigrant writing. This paper examines Mira Jacob, a Keralan woman writer who grew up in the U.S. Her parents had migrated to the US from Kerala in the late 1960s. *The Sleepwalker's Guide to Dancing* (2014) narrates the life of an Indian immigrant family in New Mexico and the dilemma of two generations of immigrants who resist assimilation. In contrast, *Good Talk: A Memoir in Conversations* (2019) explores the writer's inner life as an American first-generation citizen. This paper seeks to examine critically how Jacob's works capture the core essence of the immigrant experience from the point of view of a Malayali who was born and brought up in the United States.

Keywords: Migration, Kerala, Malayali identity, Identity Crisis, Women diaspora.

Introduction

Kerala, with its long history of immigration, has failed to record much of these experiences in literature. Only very recently has literature from the diasporic experience been considered a part of mainstream literature. This paper seeks to critically examine the portrayal of displacement and memory by the Malayali diaspora in the US by analysing the literary contributions of Mira Jacob, an Indian writer with roots in Kerala who was born in New Mexico. Her parents had migrated to the US in the late 1960s. This study also aims to compare and contrast the experiences of both first-generation and second-generation Malayali immigrants in the United States, highlighting the differences and similarities in their cultural identity,

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nostalgia, and reimagining of their homeland.

Examining the historical migration of Malayalees and the contributing circumstances is crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the context. The trajectory shows that the initial migration of Malayalees was to Burma and Singapore. However, there is little documentation of writing from this early phase. The writings of M.K. Menon, also known by his pen name Vilasini, are a distinct source that provides insights into Malayalees' daily existence in Malaysia. The travelogues of S.K. Pottekadu were exceptional in documenting the experiences of the diaspora community. Apart from these contributions in the early years of migration, there were hardly any major literary works within the diasporic context.

The 1970s saw the "Gulf Boom" in Kerala, characterised by the mass migration of Malayalees to the Gulf in search of employment. Kerala's economy, totally dependant on the money inflow from Gulf migrants, has brought substantial transformations in the social and economic structure of the state. Rajan and Zachariah point out that "according to Kerala migration surveys, about 90 per cent of Kerala migrants leave for the Gulf for temporary contract employment. The Gulf does not provide citizenship, and they all have to return to Kerala once their contract expires" (12). This initial phase of migration to the Gulf comprised semi and unskilled labourers who went to work in the construction and agriculture sector.

Factors such as the First Gulf War exerted a certain degree of influence on the trajectory of migration; subsequently, distinct migration patterns emerged. Even then, menial and semi-skilled labour migration to the Gulf persisted. Rajan and Zachariah assert that "emigration from Kerala is falling, and return migration is rising. The long history of migration from Kerala to the Gulf is in its final phase. However, remittances to the state have increased. This is because Keralites in the gulf have climbed the social ladder and are earning higher wages, allowing them to remit more" (63).

Over time, the financial stability gained by Keralites in the Gulf facilitated broader international movements, particularly to the United States. This later phase saw skilled professionals, especially IT experts and doctors, migrating for career advancements and even further education. Furthermore, many families relocated to the

host country with their spouses, who could financially support their families.

Recent trends highlight a remarkable surge in the number of students migrating from Kerala to other nations. In 2012, the number of Indian students abroad was 40 lakh, a figure expected to surpass 75 lakh in 2025, with a substantial portion being Keralites (Rajagopal). This growth reflects the evolving landscape of migration from Kerala and its diverse impact on global demographics.

Migration appears to have had a significant role in Kerala's history and economics, yet there are very few written records about these experiences. Whatever is being documented tends not to be included in the canon of conventional literature. Malayalam writer Mukundan feels that "many good writers are emerging from Gulf countries and America and are considered a part of mainstream Malayalam literature. He gives the example of the book *Goat Days* by Benyamin, which won the Kerala Sahitya Akademi Award in 2009". (344). Benyamin opines "that there was a time when the work of the migrants was not accepted in Kerala. The mere pictures of Dubai on book covers made people hesitant to buy them. The trend has changed, and he feels it is due to their hard work. Their works are considered no less than mainstream literature" (Rafeek).

Malayali Diaspora literature is currently gaining popularity and is considered a part of the conventional literature. It is represented both in English and in Malayalam, and many such writers who write in English are well-known across the world but are seldom distinguished by their Malayali identity.

The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A Close reading of the works of Mira Jacob

Mira Jacob is a novelist, memoirist, illustrator and cultural critic with her roots in Kerala, India. Her parents, who hail from Kerala, migrated to the US in the late 1960s after their marriage, and she was born and brought up in New Mexico. The parents settled in New Mexico, U.S., at a time when there were very few South Asian families in the state. Jacob and her brother grew up in a mostly American setting due to the limited presence of Indian Americans in New Mexico. This frequently caused others to assume that she was of Native American descent. She was profoundly exposed to

Indian traditions and culture through her parents, who were deeply fond of their homeland.

Jacob's literary repertoire discusses the dynamics of familial relationships, love, multiculturalism, the complexities of race, and concerns surrounding religion and identity. Her works also address the quintessential dilemma all diasporic people face: determining where they truly belong. In an interview with Amy S. Choi, Jacob remarked, "For a long time, I didn't write about my experiences because I felt I didn't know enough about being American or about being Indian. And at some point, I accepted that I just know what I know."

The Sleepwalker's Guide to Dancing (2014), her first novel, narrates the story of the Eapen family. The story begins when Amina Eapen, a talented photographer based in Seattle, is summoned to her childhood home in New Mexico. Her abrupt return is due to her father's peculiar behaviour, with reports suggesting he is conversing with ghosts. Thomas asserts that he sees and communicates with the spirits of departed family members, causing apprehension to his dear and near ones.

Amina is the daughter of Thomas Eapen and Kamala Eapen and the sister of Akhil Eapen, who was born in India and then later relocated to America, whereas Amina was born in New Mexico. Thomas and Kamala have complex feelings about their cultural roots and life in the United States. The novel explores their relationship with Kerala and the impact of their cultural heritage on their lives. While there are moments of nostalgia and a deep connection to Kerala, challenges and complexities are associated with being an immigrant in the United States. Thomas and Kamala always struggle to uphold their cultural identity, even while attempting to assimilate into American society to prevent any sense of estrangement.

Kamala and Thomas have a "hyphenated identity". As Alghaberi and Mukherjee argue in their article "The Diasporic Experience in Mira Jacob's *The Sleepwalker's Guide to Dancing: Assimilation, Memory, and Mourning*":

Jacob's characters of first-generation immigrants struggle with whether to maintain a particular identity or transform it further. Remaining hyphenated, as in the case of the parents Kamala and

Thomas in the novel, who immigrated to the United States in the 60s, creates an identity crisis. More importantly, revisiting the past and taking responsibility for individual and familial decisions determine their engagement with the American culture and society. Their choice of whether to adopt either pole of the hyphen complicates their diasporic experience, very often triggering memories and instituting moments of guilt and remorse. (638)

The novel aptly represents the contrasting attitudes of the first-generation and second-generation immigrants through the characters Thomas and Kamala and their children. Thomas and Kamala, born and brought up in Kerala and having moved to the US only after their marriage, aspire to maintain their Keralan identity and are conscious of how they adapt to the new culture. There is a genuine desire to resist the American culture and be authentically “Indian”. At the same time, they are also worried about being alienated from the host country. They try to inculcate the same attitudes in their children, wanting them to live by the values of the Indian culture. The prominent cultural indicators like food, clothing, and rituals are their everyday reality, contributing to their sense of identity, belonging and cultural heritage. On the other hand, Amina and Akhil are exposed to the Indian culture only through their parents. Outside their home, they have limited interaction with fellow Indians/Keralites and are mostly surrounded by Americans. So, they struggle to reach a middle path, battling between the “home” their parents expose them to and the actual home they see.

The depiction of three deaths in the novel symbolises the profound sense of helplessness experienced by immigrants. Thomas losing his mother and brother in India adds more complexity, emphasising the challenge of being far from home during such difficult times. Grief further aggravates the feeling of alienation in the host country, where the migrant longs for a sense of belonging in their host country. Thomas’s struggles and lasting pain from these losses reflect a common theme in the immigrant experience: finding a balance between creating a new identity and holding onto cultural roots.

Mira Jacob stated, “I wrote the book for people like me, who have always been invisible. And for mixed-race families who feel really

torn up every single day in this country and can't see themselves" (Olufson). It is evident from her statement that she has experiences of feeling overlooked or unseen within her society. Her writing echoes her desire to give voices to those who have been ignored. She understands the challenges faced by individuals who grapple between multiple cultural and racial identities.

Good Talk: A Memoir in Conversations, Jacob's second book, is a graphic memoir that explores race, identity, and family, through personal anecdotes and social commentary. The work takes the form of a series of conversations between Jacob and her six-year-old son Zakir, who constantly asks her questions about racism. In order to explain to him the realities, she devised this in the form of a graphic memoir instead of an essay. The book addresses issues like the complexities of racial identity, the difficulties of negotiating cross-cultural relationships, the existence of a brown-skinned New Yorker after 9/11, the effects of Donald Trump's administration on people of colour, etc. Here Mira Jacob delves into the experiences of a third-generation immigrant through her son Zakir who has an even more complex identity as his father is a Jew, and his mixed identity is the reason why the six-year-old asks about racism at a young age.

Conclusion

Mira Jacob has effectively portrayed the life of the Malayali diaspora in the US through her works, especially in her debut novel. She narrates the issues of displacement and trauma faced by both first- and second-generation immigrants, drawing from her background as a second-generation immigrant born to parents who migrated to the US after marriage. Unlike the Gulf diaspora, immigrants in the US often settle permanently due to the country's perceived advantages and opportunities, forming a lasting community that spans generations. The novel's background serves as a metaphor for her own life. Having settled in the US herself, Jacob now unfolds the narrative as a third-generation migrant through her child. Her work unveils the immigrant experience, particularly exploring Malayali identity in the United States. Through her storytelling, she captures the evolution of generations, the intricacies of cultural adaptation, and the continuous reshaping of immigrant identity in a new homeland.

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